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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Report on the involvement of local Stakeholders

- Deliverable D6.3 -

Chelli, R.1, Stoduto, E1., Zipoli, M¹.

¹ UNIMED, Mediterranean Universities Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

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Document Information

Grant Agreement #:	822688
Project Title:	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
Project Acronym:	RAISD
Project Start Date:	1 st February, 2019
Related work package:	WP 6: Action-research development
Deliverable:	D6.3 Report on the involvement of local Stakeholders
Related task(s):	Task 6.4 Involvement of local stakeholders
Lead Organisation:	WPL UNIMED Responsible for Deliverable UNIMED
Submission date:	30/06/2022
Dissemination Level:	Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (Notes)
31/03/2022	UNIMED	UCM	Review 1
14/04/2022	All partners	UNIMED	Review 2
05/05/2022	UNIMED	All partners	Review 3
30/06/2022	UNIMED	UCM	Version 1 - uploaded

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D6.3 Report on the involvement of local Stakeholders [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , gracia.fdi.ucm.es

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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Coordinator contact:

Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Avda. de Séneca, 2. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.

t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es/grasia.fdi.ucm.es

Executive Summary

The goal of this document is to perform an ex-post analysis of the most relevant issues concerning the involvement of both local and international stakeholders in the RAISD project activities, through their cooperation with the Partners and in the ARUs. Beyond the design and implementation of the TAIS, ARUs made great achievements also thanks to the participation of all stakeholders throughout the entire project lifespan.

The very nature of the project and especially of the TAISs as one of its most relevant outputs, calls for a deep and wide involvement of a very diversified range of local stakeholders such as academics, researchers, NGOs, service providers, business company and even local public authorities, whereas it must be emphasized that the role of these stakeholders is vital in order to ensure the sustainability of the whole action. Also FDP and vulnerable groups have been represented in the activities of the project, both as active actors and beneficiaries.

In this frame, this document is based on the collection of information from a series of previous deliverables and surveys, and on the outcome of a specific survey which was executed with the goal of collecting missing information about the engagement and involvement of stakeholders in the RAISD project.

Therefore, the document starts by illustrating the methodology which has been applied to its elaboration, explaining the information sources and how they were processed.

It then reports the main inputs provided by the members of the external Advisory Board on the stakeholders' engagement, which are particularly valuable being the expression of an independent view. The subsequent session focuses on analysing in which ways the stakeholders were selected and involved in the ARUs and TAISs.

The next section summarises the outcomes of the involvement of external stakeholders in the three cross-pilots organised by CESIE in order to create synergies among the different ARUs. It then analyses the main activities performed by the ARUs in addition to the implementation of the TAIS.

Subsequently it analyses two key aspects in terms of sustainability, namely the continuous involvement of the ARUs members and of the other stakeholders also after the end of the funding period.

The document concludes with the analysis of how two concrete outputs of the project will have an impact on sustainability, namely the trainings delivered as part of WP6 and the Observatory.

Finally some conclusions are drawn for the work depicted above.

1 Deliverable methodological approach

This document, titled “D6.3 Report on the involvement of local stakeholders” is the main deliverable stemming out of task T6.4 “Task 6.4 Involvement of local stakeholders”, which is defined as follows in the Description of Work of the RAISD project:

Task 6.4 Involvement of local stakeholders

T6.4 will also work in the involvement of the local stakeholders, e.g. members of VGs, civil society or policy makers. The long-term sustainability of the works depends on creating a local network of actively involved actors. These will observe, participate, and provide feedback on the activities of their local ARU and the overall project, as well as contribute to their local promotion. This task includes for each ARU:

- Selecting relevant local stakeholders, with a particular focus on civil society, to promote the involvement of the host community.
- Developing specific materials (e.g. summaries of VG situation, activities and results) and activities (e.g. visits and participation) to boost their interest.
- Inviting stakeholders, when relevant, to join the ARU.
- Evaluating the level of involvement of local stakeholders.

The description of these items constitutes D6.3.

According to this definition, the task leader UNIMED adopted the following methodology.

The following list of issues to be addressed was defined:

1. The involvement of the Advisory Board (AB).
2. Reflection on the stakeholders that have been involved by the ARUs (research, business, decision-makers.).
3. Involvement of stakeholders in the cross-pilot workshops.
4. Activities other than the TAISs and who has been involved by the ARUs.

The sources of information were:

- i. The results of an ad-hoc survey which was circulated to the ARU leaders.
- ii. For Item 1 above: AB minutes of the two Plenary Meetings where AB members were involved (September 2020 and November 2021).
- iii. For item 2 above: ad-hoc survey and previous deliverables D7.1 and D7.2.
- iv. For Item 3 above: reports of the cross-pilot workshops.
- v. For Item 4 above: from the ad-hoc survey.

The information was collected and analysed. For each one of the above mentioned issues, the corresponding section of the deliverable was compiled addressing all the seven ARUs. Finally, a number of overall conclusions were drawn. In the document we provide details on each of the above-mentioned focused section.

2 The involvement of the Advisory Board

The Advisory Board members have collaborated specifically as participants in two consortium meetings, but also during many more occasions, sharing feedbacks and inputs on the project activities, as well as in different ARU meetings and in other consultations. Moreover, AB members will participate in the Final Conference (foreseen in Palermo in May 2022), and have participated in 3 cross-analysis workshops (as reported in the dedicated session).

The AB members were directly involved on the occasion of two partnership meetings in September 2020 and in November 2021.

The main inputs from the AB members as regards Stakeholders' involvement and sustainability are summarised below. The main stakeholders' groups mentioned by the members of the AB are underlined.

- Outputs from the project should be cross-read in partner countries: students, scholars, policy practitioners should be aware of the results of RAISD partners in other countries. This calls for a wider and more effective communication beyond the traditional circle of stakeholders.
- NGOs and service providers that implemented the TAIS or participated in the ARUs' work should try to apply the findings to their daily practice. This calls for a continued support and monitoring by the local ARU leaders after the end of the project.
- It must be emphasised that the immense efforts of project partners should be heard by the decision/policy makers. Hence a well-designed mainstreaming campaign should be implemented.
- Some NGOs and humanitarian agencies should be empowered at EC level. The humanitarian work has many challenges in terms of immigration issues. Those challenges should be shown by the mass media. Here, the role of media as a stakeholder is emphasised and should be taken into account in the future communication.
- Sustainability is the core element of the project concerning migration issues. A real collaboration among the local governmental bodies and other actors is a must.
- Again, on the role of Media: Media should be involved to spread awareness of refugees and other vulnerable group's issues.
- Supporting different public sectors (schools, hospitals, health centres, malls and small supermarkets, etc.) to be able to include more vulnerable persons.
- Organisational level (NGOs, Humanitarian agencies) in each country should be directly involved and/or sensitised.
- Spread awareness of those vulnerable groups' traits and needs that may assist to be more acceptable, and positively included in the society (hosting community). This would change the wrong perspectives that lead to see them as emotionally and physically handicapped, and instead, reinforce their empowerment.

There are several ways that can be followed to ensure the sustainability of the RAISD project:

- Activate the cooperation with Psychology department at Yarmouk University, to ensure engaging master and PhD students in providing counselling Psychology services through the platform and website established.
- Activate the role of refugees and displaced persons at Yarmouk University and carry out research on the urgent related topics.
- It is also important to establish national/local observation hubs that include local stakeholders and their participation. This would empower local contexts and bring more effectiveness to the local-regional efforts.
- The greatest impact could be reached at local level, contacting Mayors and civil servants who might be eager to forward the recommendations to those who are in the position of doing something.
- In Italy, as a cultural feature, all aspects of public life are still very much relation-based, but of course it is not the same in all countries. Hence, the recommendations should be forwarded through formal and informal channels, maybe also developing a document that could be signed by the representatives of local diaspora communities.
- Possibility to develop a database or contact list of the NGOs and civil societies organisations that were engaged during the project.
- Although ARUs include representatives of these groups, it will be important to increase the number of participants such as researchers, policy makers and NGOs.
- It needs to be mentioned that most TAISs activities do not emphasise the role and the potential of the media, despite the fact that media could change the context in which the TAISs operate.

In summary, all the members of the Advisory Board highlighted the importance of involving a wide range of stakeholders, including the media, the local governments, and the civil society organisations in order to support the sustainability of the action. This recommendation has been taken into account by project Partners, in particular in the final phases of the project to ensure sustainability of results, and with the organisation of the final Conference.

3 Reflection on the stakeholders that have been involved

While building the Action-Research Units, partners followed a number of guidelines which mainly focused on including a wide range of different actors and stakeholders representing the quintuple helix. To do so, and to rely on a strong expertise for the co-design of the TAISs and the definition of the vulnerability contexts, partners leveraged on their previous experiences in research projects and initiatives with vulnerable groups. Welcoming actors and experts from different fields ensured a solid base to the ARUs, followed by an ongoing process of engagement of previous and new stakeholders.

ARUs allow all voices to be heard and contribute to strengthening the dialogue among members themselves. Difficulties were found by some of the ARUs in reaching all types of stakeholders of the Quintuple Helix, especially the private sector and government bodies. In fact, those ARUs which managed to involve a wide range of stakeholders representing the Quintuple Helix felt stronger in their action.

The variable composition of the ARU could be considered as a problem, especially because in many cases the members of the same ARU changed over time, thus reducing the common knowledge about the TAIS and the mutual knowledge among the ARU members. However, the inclusion of new members upon necessity has been a positive unexpected outcome.

Language problems were also a major component in communicating with FDP (EU-based ARUs) and internally (local language vs English). Language has been a key issue in TAIS implementation with language skills being among the basic skills to be passed to FDP. Still, it stayed as a challenge for the functioning of the ARUs themselves¹.

All ARUs worked performing many meetings, at first in presence, later virtually due to the pandemic outbreak. During the meetings ARU members worked together for the definition of the vulnerability contexts in which they were going to operate, and to co-design the TAIS. All ARUs reported that different actors were actively involved making all voices heard. Decision-making was shared among the core ARU members, and decisions were reported to everyone.

Adaptations were needed and all ARUs reported the great capacity of the working groups to adapt in the most effective ways.

In terms of challenges, many ARUs identified problems related to the language of beneficiaries (many of them are not familiar with the local language) and to the protection of their identity, so as to create trust: it is common experience that many migrants and especially refugees are reluctant to be identified as such. Along with the RAISD ethic principles, the anonymity of the FDP has been respected all the time, and all the ethical criteria have always been complied with. Also, in some of the RAISD countries, the government is not keen in supporting migrants and this makes things more complicated².

¹ Source: D6.2 conclusions, section Building the ARUs

² Source: D6.2 conclusions, section ARUs' way of working: meetings, exchanges, and decision-making process

4 Involvement of stakeholders in the cross-pilot workshops

During the project lifetime, three cross-pilot workshops were organised by CESIE, on behalf of the whole Consortium, and with the participation of all Partners. The 3 workshops took place online on:

- 21 January 2021.
- 10 June 2021.
- 21 January 2022.

The exchange-workshops are part of the RAISD local action research-agenda, aimed at gathering new insights on “Tailored-Attention and Inclusion Strategies” (TAISs) processes in the different partner countries (Lebanon, Jordan, Turkey, Hungary, Finland, Italy and Spain) – keen to become a platform for critical multi-contexts and multi-stakeholder perspectives, reflecting on assumptions, design, evaluation-criteria and actual implementation of the TAIS piloting rounds. Becoming part of a transformative action-research process rather than a one-off event, the workshops have the potential to generate initiatives on improving several and diverse project related aspects.

1. The **first exchange-workshop in January 2021** aimed at mapping internal and external systems; their impact within and around the strategies’ contexts; identifying potential anomalies by going back to initial assumptions, ideally deconstructing them; investigating positive and negative effects rising from our action-research interventions.
2. The **second exchange workshop in June 2021** aimed at gathering constructive critical viewpoints on TAISs developments that would allow to further improve methodological aspects within and around the local attention and inclusion strategies for Highly Vulnerable Groups affected by forced displacement.
3. The **third workshop in January 2022** aimed at gathering critical viewpoints on the three implemented TAISs piloting rounds in the different partner countries: retrospective feedback followed by feed-forward responsiveness.

The overall cross-piloting analysis process involved a total of 110 stakeholders, representing 33 ARU members from the seven national project contexts (Spain, Italy, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan, Lebanon).

Figure 1. Attendees’ distribution by partner countries

Figure 2. Attendees' distribution by gender

Due to the 2020/2021 COVID-19 pandemic travel limitations, the format of the cross-pilot exchange workshops had to change from in-presence to online, but it actually permitted a much larger participation in terms of number of attendees and variety of stakeholders' profiles.

In the first cross-pilot workshop, all partner countries were represented with a total of 33 participants: 28 among ARU and AB members, plus 5 moderators. Gender balance: female 18/male 15. In addition to project partners, there were attendees from the media, from a company engaged in social and inclusive entrepreneurship, from the Red Cross, and from another university. These organisations were: Eskişehir.Net/Sedef Medya (Turkey); Fundación Nantik Lum (Spain); Red Cross Finland (Finland); Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (Turkey). Stakeholders represented all the 4 helixes: the education system, research, business, the media-based and culture-based public (also 'civil society'), as well as policy-makers at local and global level.

To the second cross-pilot workshop, all partner countries were represented with a total of 51 participants: female 60%, male 40%. During the discussion, the partners confirmed that - beyond the beneficiaries of the TAISs - the ARUs were able to mobilise and involve also NGOs in Jordan, Spain and Lebanon; local municipalities in Turkey and policy-makers in Spain; reception centres in Finland and in Italy; public sectors representatives in Jordan; academics in Spain and Turkey; business companies in Spain and Italy. In addition to project partners, the attendees were the following: Red Cross Finland (Finland); Centro per lo Sviluppo Creativo Danilo Dolci (Italy); Greater Irbid municipality (Jordan); Alfarouq (Jordan); Fundación Nantik Lum (Spain); SPR Lapin Piiri Rovaniemen vastaantokeskus (Finland); PAZ.ai (Spain); Karma Foundation for Training, Logistics and Consultations (Jordan); IRC (Jordan); Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (Turkey); Terre des hommes (Hungary).

To the third cross-pilot workshop, all partner countries were represented with a total of 26 participants: 22 among ARU and AB members, plus 4 moderators. Gender balance: female 70%, male 30%.

5 Have ARUs done activities other than TAISs and who has been involved?

The project saw the creation of 7 ARUs, one in each partner country. ARUs are multidisciplinary groups distributed throughout Central-Eastern (Hungary), Southern (Spain and Italy) and Northern (Finland) parts of Europe, Eastern Europe from Asia (Turkey) and Middle East (Jordan, Lebanon). The locally based Units were designed and built to collaborate with local organisations, researchers, and stakeholders to explore the potential difficulties of addressing both the local demands of society on the issues of FDP inclusion, and the local and global demands to contribute to a more equitable and sustainable society. In other words, ARUs were built to co-design the TAISs (Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies) as effective measures to address the inclusion of vulnerable groups.

ARUs were therefore mostly responsible for gathering information on forced migrants and their lives, and/or on other vulnerable targets, defining vulnerability contexts, and engaging with local institutions, organisations, actors for the benefit of the more vulnerable and the hosting societies as well. The main activity of the ARUs during the project implementation was the piloting of the TAIS, and the monitoring and reporting of the pilot experience. However, ARUs had the potential to do more, despite the many challenges and difficulties faced along the way, above all the COVID-19 pandemic.

Examples of activities performed by the ARUs other than the TAIS are:

- UCM, Leader of the Spanish ARU, arranged meetings to develop and compile Policy Recommendations, to represent the necessities and observations of the representatives of the quintuple helix (see below).
- The Spanish ARU has encouraged the participation of forced migrants, beneficiaries of the TAIS, in the documentary film promoted and developed by UCM.
- Teaching innovation activities with ARU members, FDP and migrants, as well as undergraduate and master students at UCM. Examples are: Talk about media discourse on migration and forced migration developed by CEAR (60 undergraduate students at UCM); Development of communication campaigns and research (service-learning experiences): Mundo en Movimiento, final beneficiaries of the TAIS, and UNHCR Spain with around 50 master and undergraduate students at UCM.
- A member of the Turkish ARU led by Anadolu University, Hüseyin Akçay, as behalf of Bar Association of Eskişehir initiated an anti-discrimination campaign with multiple stakeholders of the city.
- Beyond the TAIS, due to the pandemic outbreak, the Lebanese ARU committed to intervene widely to support health and health awareness among Syrian refugees, to cope with the spread of COVID-19. More than 30 students from the Syrian refugee camp were involved and committed to share with others.

Among the activities performed by the ARUs, beyond the specific scope of the TAISs, was to conduct research with the collaboration of the ARU members, through interviews and questionnaires about the needs and good practices derived from and arose during the pandemic, as well as their opinion on the media discourse on migration and forced migration. In Spain, thanks to the work of the Spanish ARU at the Complutense University of Madrid, these

collaborations have resulted in two papers in scientific journals, one of them published³, in a Story, Poetry and Photography contest⁴, and in the production of the RAISD Documentary "Espejismos: fragmentos del exilio" [Fragments of Exile] with the participation of 17 forced migrants in the film.

The more participated ARU was the Spanish one guided by UCM. As an example, in addition to what reported above, ARU meetings have been organized to develop and compile policy recommendations. For example:

- a) ARU meeting (online) (25/05/2021), Total of 10 people (7 women, 3 men) from 8 different organizations:
 - Alcobendas City Council. Coordinator for the Promotion of Equality (policymaker)
 - Provivienda (NGO)
 - CEAR (NGO)
 - ACCEM (NGO)
 - Rey Juan Carlos University (Education, Research, and Media)
 - Instituto de Migraciones (IUEM) (Research)
 - La Merced (NGO)
 - Mundo en Movimiento (NGO)

- b) ARU meeting (online) (2/12/2021). Total of 10 people (7 women, 3 men) from 10 different organizations:
 - Provivienda (NGO)
 - Alcobendas City Council. Coordinator for the Promotion of Equality (policy-maker)
 - La Merced (NGO)
 - Asociación Empleo y Desarrollo (Business and NGO)
 - La Rueda (NGO and policymaker)
 - Mundo en Movimiento (NGO)
 - Instituto de Migraciones (IUEM) (Research)
 - Rey Juan Carlos University (Education, Research, and Media)
 - ACCEM (NGO)
 - CEAR (NGO)

³ Bueno Doral, T., Lara, M. and García-Castillo, N. (2021), "Social care for the migrant population in Spain: needs and strengths of organisations during the COVID-19 pandemic and infodemic", International Journal of Migration, Health and Social Care, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMHS-10-2020-0097>

⁴ More information available in <https://www.facebook.com/espejismoswebdoc/> and https://instagram.com/espejismoswebdoc?utm_medium=copy_link

6 Quantitative data on stakeholders' involvement

The statistics about the participation of both final beneficiaries and stakeholders (intended as organisations participating in the work of the ARUs and in the implementation of TAIS) are shown in Annex I and II below.

Needless to say, the statistics provided are heavily influenced by the extreme heterogeneity of the contexts of the ARUs and of the specific contents of the TAIS and other different activities which have been implemented.

Thus, for instance it comes as no surprise that in TAIS II for Finland the number of “other” beneficiaries was zero as the action was very much focussed on the action of the Red Cross.

However, all in all we can make the following considerations:

- On the average, the gender balance in the TAIS implementation team was largely positive in terms of female participation. This was the result of a clear decision in this direction by the whole consortium which was then implemented by all partners.
- The gender balance as regards the participants is fair on the average, in some cases it was biased by the way the TAIS was conceived, e.g., when it was decided to address women as the target group.
- Also, the number of “other beneficiaries” which would benefit directly or indirectly from the TAIS varies from zero in some cases to more than 100 in other cases, again due to the high diversity of the TAIS contents: however, the total number of beneficiaries is generally speaking very high testifying of how the project had a significant impact on its context.

7 How to keep ARU members involved over time

Basically, and as stressed by the project coordinator (UCM), the Observatory (more in formation in the dedicated paragraph) is one of the main aspects for keeping the ARU members involved over time and after the project ends.

The project includes sustainability plans for the TAIS-related research methodology, especially in terms of keeping on researching current Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) for FDP and diverse vulnerability contexts. This is the core objective of the RAISD Observatory on Forced Migration, an international collaborative organism created among project partners that has already started its activity in March 2021 and that will continue working after the project finishes, with local branches and activities in project countries.

For the **Spanish ARU**, other initiatives related to the project, such as teaching innovation activities, with ARU members, FDP and migrants, as well as undergraduate and master students at UCM, will surely have a continuation in the future. UCM team will study the possibility of applying for funding to start new responsible research and innovation projects related to vulnerable groups, and where interested ARU members are invited to participate.

For all the aspects of future sustainability (as well as RAISD methodology compliance), the ARUs must be maintained throughout all the project, even after the TAIS finish their action. For example, the collaboration can continue by collecting policy recommendations, developing other initiatives (as mentioned above) and collecting ideas for the Observatory financing and actions. ARU members of all the consortium have a key role in sustaining the Observatory, which will be largely based on the volunteer work of project partners.

Some practical ideas emerged during one of the Consortium Meetings in which Advisory Board members and RAISD partners shared inputs for the future sustainability and the Observatory such as:

- Especially small NGOs (many of the ARU members) are particularly interested in the project and in the TAIS practices, get inspiration and tools from the project. Therefore, it would be good for them to receive future training and resources from the Observatory. Also, the Observatory could collect the dissemination activities of the AB and ARU members, where they mention RAISD and talk about forced migration.
- It is hard to keep the action going without incentives, but this doesn't need to be monetary. Students are easy to engage, teachers can use the resources and ideas from the project (available at the Observatory website) for their lessons and projects. Also, FDP can be engaged as volunteers.
- Some of the project activities (TAIS) could be turned into field activities in the Syrian refugee camps in Lebanon and other countries.
- Reaching policy makers and offering concrete solutions would make the project more sustainable (and keep ARUs engaged).

- Networking and exchanging information, knowledge, and practices, making research data accessible for new studies and organising events, such as Research for Change⁵, would make the Observatory feasible and interesting for the ARU members.

On the other hand, as has been specified in other deliverables, the Spanish TAIS might be replicated with some changes, even in other vulnerable groups among the FDP or other social groups.

In the case of the **Italian ARU**, it will continue working on the research question, raised after the literature, policy review, interviews, and pilot activities: What are the most effective educational inclusion strategies for increasing participation and continuity in education among highly vulnerable displaced people currently living in the region of Sicily?

The AUCL Strategy and its online infrastructure will continue operating after the end of the project as the ARU aims to further target-tailor and enhance the Learning Objectives to select from, increment the number of users and diversify HVG profiles that can benefit from it. Given the flexible nature of the TAIS (AUCL), all thematic units are encouraged to use the tool with their own specific target groups, and this will in turn encourage transferability and sustainability of the TAIS. To contribute to the future of the RAISD project, the ARU Observatory will allow for discussion, sharing, multiplication and transferability of the innovative concept at regional and national level. The AUCL (Italian TAIS) is expected to (a) generate genuine and sustainable improvements in the Learning and Training Environments (formal and non-formal) and (b) improve the situation of Highly Vulnerable target groups regarding educational attainment, social inclusion and well-being. The TAIS ensures sustainability as the AUCL Platform is based on CESIE's server, thus its updating and maintenance will not require additional funding resources at the end of RAISD's project lifetime. Moreover, the tool allows adopting and adapting knowledge resources that have been developed and approved within European project context in many years of activity.

The **Finnish ARU** has worked on two pilots. The first one - the Multilingual Online forum - and its sustainability can see the continuous involvement of, at least, the Finnish Red Cross since they should be involved by convincing them that the strategy implemented can be feasible and it has the potential to continue as it represents a new channel to recruit and engage male volunteers which has been an enduring problem for the Red Cross for decades and beside online forum offers a light way of volunteer work not requiring lots of invested time or long-term commitments. Consequently, it is one potential answer to the problem of decreasing NGO participation rate in Finland.

For the second pilot about the child-care services, the model developed within the project and that has been an integration in already existing structures, has the potential to be used in reception centres throughout Finland. This model will help the coordinating authorities (the Finnish Migration Service and the Finnish Red Cross) and other local actors (reception centres) to implement quality child-care services in other settings as well. For this consideration for both pilots, the involvement of the ARU members after the end of the project seems to be very possible.

In the **Hungarian ARU** the collaboration among the involved members had since the beginning the form of a long-term collaboration. During the project, the core research team paid attention to including ARU members connected to vulnerable refugees from various professional points of view. These different experiences of the ARU and the

⁵ More on the event: <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research-for-change/>

various roles they played in several segments of the care system were significant resources and motivators for each actor in the project.

Due to the joint work, different collaborations independent of the TAIS have also been developed. The level of interorganisational trust has increased according to the ARU members, the development process of TAIS also generated further collaborations, resulting in not only the better cooperation of the professionals but it also guaranteed the multiplication of the TAIS products ensuring long-term sustainability. An ARU member pointed out that the cooperation can work with daily dialogues and common discussion forums. In Hungary there is a considerable network of civil society organisations, forming for more than 20 years, that work in the field of refugee integration and advocacy. The ARU covers most of this cluster. The self-interest of these organisations is to keep ties with each other, as well as with central and local government representatives, the business sector, and the academia.

In the **Jordanian ARU**, the way to keep the involvement of members overtime will be to share the results of the TAIS. Few of them have started using the TAIS outputs in their work. To ease this process, training, and support was also offered and, in fact, training in evaluation methods has been provided. Also documents about RAISD methodology will be translated in Arabic.

In the **Lebanese ARU**, one of the elements to grant sustainability of the ARU, and to enforce the future perspective of the research unit, is to nurture a broad base of community support, building and maintaining diverse supportive stakeholder's groups through:

- Continue to involve local leaders from business, government, faith-based organisations, non-profit NGOs, and others throughout the TAIS implementation and the activities of the ARU.
- Form partnerships with organisations that serve the same population, be clear on new roles and responsibilities, and establish or revise memoranda of understanding, if appropriate.
- Build positive relationships with local media.
- Start imagining future joint actions.
- Include the youth and families served during the project.
- Develop leadership skills of key stakeholders (ARU members) so they can educate others about the project and the inclusion strategies put in place.

8 How to keep the target group / beneficiaries involved over time

In this section we analyse some of the factors which will support the sustainability of the action after the end of the funding period, focussing on target groups and final beneficiaries. It must be understood that among the target groups we also involve the main stakeholders which have participated in the ARUs.

The following paragraphs include the information provided by the ARU leaders regarding this topic. At the end of this section, we summarise the main findings. It must be noted that this is an update of the information provided in the previous Deliverable D6.2 on sustainability.

Spain

The women that have participated in the entrepreneurship and coaching program, as well as other FDP that are potential direct beneficiaries of the different TAISs could be interested in joining the observatory or staying informed through it. Due to that, they will be informed when the Observatory is more developed. Also, some potential beneficiaries (belonging to other VGs among the FDP) have shown their interest in the observatory.

On the other hand, by “target group / final beneficiaries” we could understand the different members of the quintuple helix, so stakeholders in general. Some initiatives of the ARU can be prolonged in time. However, the main future perspective of the ARU is the online Observatory.

Other initiatives related to the project, such as teaching innovation activities, with ARU members, FDP and migrants, as well as undergraduate and master students at UCM, will surely have a continuation in the future.

Italy/CESIE

The Competence Cell exploited the TAIS knowledge and know-how under two recently approved different follow up projects to ensure continuity to the target group and final beneficiaries, within the frame of AMIF programme (Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund) [Start: 01/02/2022 – End: 31/01/2024]:

- PITCH: A model for gender-sensitive integration strategies based on Personalised, local, and multi-stakeholder approaches AMIF-2020-AG (project coordinator CESIE).
- WINGS: Supporting Women survivors of trafficking through a Comprehensive Integration Programme AMIF-2020-AG (project coordinator CESIE, <https://cesie.org/en/project/wings/>).

Moreover, other ongoing CESIE projects that continue keeping involved the target group and final beneficiaries, in a direct or indirect way, are:

CESIE's Unit 'Rights and Justice':

- CEAR – Community Engagement Against Radicalisation.
- ISEX – Integral Sexual Education and Empowerment in Schools.

- HEAL – enHancing rEcovery and integrAtion through networking, empLoyment training and psychological support for women victims of trafficking.
- STOP! – Sexual child abuse prevention: New methods, topics and approaches in European context.
- Children First – Addressing Gender Based Violence from the bottom-up.
- BASE Migrant and refugee child-friendly support services in cases of sexual and gender-based violence.
- TOLERANT – TransnatiOnAL network for Employment integRAtion of womE n vicTims of trafficking.

CESIE's Unit 'Migration':

- CIVILHOOD – Enhancing unaccompanied minors' transition to early adulthood through civic education and labour market integration.
- DIGIMI – DIGital storytelling for Migrant Integration.
- 3STEPS – Fostering Education and Inclusion of disadvantages refugee and migrant learners.
- ENACTED – European Network of Active Civil socieTy for Education and Diversity.
- LIAISON – Mutual Learning for Intercultural Appreciation and Strengthened Organisational Networks.
- INCLUSIVE EUROPE – Build Bonds Not Walls.
- DIGIMI – DIGital storytelling for Migrant Integration.
- Digital Practices for Inclusive Programs.

Finland

Final beneficiaries are asylum seekers who either have to leave the country, resort to living as an undocumented person or relocate after a (positive) decision. In any case, final beneficiaries are highly mobile, their interests probably change quite drastically, and they are difficult to reach after a while. Asylum seekers come and go. Consequently, the Finnish sub-project aims to involve the service providers for more long-term purposes. However, the following statements regarding sustainability have been formulated in the previous survey and still hold true:

- The elements hindering sustainability are related to the shortness of the trial of more intensive childcare services. However, the TAIS had also elements supporting future sustainability.
- Firstly, even though the amount of the services would decrease back to the level they were before the trial in the co-operative reception centre, the services will not entirely finish. The qualitative improvement of the services carried out during the development process will sustain in ongoing child-care services of the reception centre. Moreover, the reception centre now has the experience and model of providing more intensive child-care services, thus, they can be easily widened if the recourses increase again in the future.

Actually, the reception centre is hoping for the trial and the documentation of the development work and its results to justify more stable provision on more intensive child-care.

- Secondly, the model of child-care services established in the project can be utilised in reception centres throughout Finland. The modelling will help the coordinating authorities (the Finnish Migration Service and Finnish Red Cross) and other local actors (reception centres) to implement quality child-care services in other settings as well.
- Thirdly, the outcome of the TAIS proves the importance and advantage of regular child-care services for asylum-seeking families. These results can be used in advocacy work to argue for more regular child-care services in reception centres and/or for guaranteeing asylum-seeking children's access to municipal early childhood and care services.

Hungary

The Hungarian NGO and service provider scene that is active in the asylum and integration area is rather small, so there is a mutual interest in its members to continue cooperation. All these stakeholders are in direct contact with FDPs living in Hungary, so the tools developed by the Hungarian TAIS can help, through the activity of ARU members, to provide better services to the target group and to engage them in activities organised by these institutions that can help their social integration.

The following information provided in the TAIS Final Report is also of interest here:

During the project, the core research team paid attention to including ARU members connected to vulnerable refugees: the different experiences of the members and the various roles they played in several segments of the care system were significant resources and motivators for each actor in the project, and increased the level of inter-organisational. Collaborations, professionalism and dialogue made the TAIS a potentially replicable and transferable experience, ensuring long-term perspective to the action. In Hungary there is a considerable network of civil society organizations, forming for more than 20 years, but it requires forums like the ARU meetings to maintain these ties. NGOs have developed a resilient network that surrounds the individual in need of assistance, and it can be hoped that the self-interest of these organisations will keep the spirit of cooperation alive even after the end of the project.

Turkey

AU plans to develop a monitoring hub and monitoring tool with the cooperation of Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality with the data obtained within the scope of TAIS implementation. Thus, the involvement of the target group and final beneficiaries will be ensured after the project. As already pointed out before, the role of the Observatory will be key to support the sustainability of the action.

Lebanon

For sustainability, the idea is to constantly set ongoing meetings and look for any social and educational gaps. Lebanon is going through severe vulnerability and what has been done in RAISD could be replicated on other areas of the Lebanese context.

Furthermore, it must be reminded that one of the elements to sustainability in the strive for future survivability and the key for the future ARUs perspective is nurture a broad base of community support by building and maintaining diverse and supportive stakeholder groups/networks through involving local leaders from business, government, faith-based organisations, non-profit NGOs, and others such like during the life of the RAISD project: form partnerships with organisations that serve the same population, be clear on new roles and responsibilities, build positive relationships with local media and work towards including youth and families we served during the project. All the while developing leadership skills of the key stakeholders so they can educate others about the project.

Jordan

We have two groups of final beneficiaries: ARU members and refugees. YU shares the TAIS result among ARU members, few of them started using the TAIS outputs in their work. Ethically, YU-team is ready to provide any help and support to any one of the ARU members who needs that. Few ARU members asked for training in evaluation methods and YU will prepare for that. Refugees were connected through our TAIS implementation with local NGOs who provide services related to their needs. And these NGOs will keep working with them and providing them psychological support using the TAIS outputs.

Italy/UNIMED

UNIMED is the only RAISD partner which did not implement an ARU as they were involved in the setting up of the ARUs and in their monitoring. In this frame UNIMED made a significant effort in designing and implementing the training path for the members of the ARUs covering a wide range of topics related to the work with VGs and FDPs. All these trainings were recorded and are available both on the YouTube channel and on UNIMED's E-learning platform and they will obviously remain available in the future, as a sustainability pathway for the project's results. Furthermore, UNIMED will definitely contribute to the implementation and dissemination of the Observatory after the end of the project and is highly committed to exploiting all the knowledge acquired, the best practices collected, and the lessons learnt from the implementation of the TAIS and other results of RAISD derived from the ARUs in all the future projects in the same area.

9 Summary of the main findings

In summary, the main findings about the sustainability of the action as far as the engagement of target groups and stakeholders is concerned are:

- Most of the actors recognised the involvement of media as a key element for promoting the involvement of stakeholders and target groups also after the end of the project. Although for the latter, and in particular for some final beneficiaries of the TAISs as FDP and Vulnerable Groups there are confidentiality issues as regards communication. During the project lifespan, ethics principles (including anonymization) have been always followed for the involvement of vulnerable participants and FDP. The involvement of mass media, considered as stakeholders, is considered vital for the future sustainability of the project's results. This fact should be born in mind in designing the future sustainability plans by the RAISD partners.
- The RAISD Observatory is welcomed as a strong element of the sustainability of the actions: past experiences have shown that a permanent structure, even if only online, created to foster loyalty among actors interested in the issues addressed by the project, is the best way to keep the results alive.
- It is quite obvious that the involvement of civil society, especially through local NGOs and local actors, is another key element of the sustainability of the action.
- The online trainings which are available to all interested actors and will be kept online by UNIMED for the next few years is also a relevant element to invite other actors to exploit the project's results.
- As a concluding remark, one of the main problems to be solved is how to motivate the target groups and stakeholders to stay in touch with the project's results. It is clear from the above that a strong communication action is needed specially to highlight the usefulness and beneficial effects of exploiting the project's results.

10 Key tools for stakeholders' involvement: the RAISD training

At project level a training course was developed by UNIMED after having discussed the proposal with the project coordinator and the rest of the partners. A total of 7 modules were developed and held online from November 2020 and up to February 2021, hosted on the UNIMED Zoom platform. All the lectures were recorded and uploaded on UNIMED YouTube Channel, on the RAISD project website, and on the UNIMED e-learning platform.

M1 – Participatory Approach and Inclusive communication skills.

M2 – Applying Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) Principles (2 sessions with the same trainer).

M3 – Adaptation to Covid-19: Creative Commons (CC), Open Educational Resources (OER) and practical Online Teaching with Technology (3 sessions with the same trainer).

M4 – Gender Issues in the Mediterranean region (5 sessions with different trainers).

M5 – Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) evaluation procedures.

M6 – Funding for projects on Vulnerable groups.

M7 – Psychological Support and Trauma Management (2 session with the same trainer).

The training was addressed to the staff working at the ARUs and committed to implement the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) for selected vulnerable groups. The training opportunities are intended to support inclusion actors to gain knowledge and skills on a wide range of topics that might be needed in their path towards innovative attention and inclusion strategies, tailored upon the vulnerability context in which they operate.

The training includes session approaching horizontal topics – which are more general issues of interest for all local ARUs, and vertical topics related to the particular work of specific TAIS developments. The learning outcomes can be summarised as follows:

- Developing an advanced expertise to effectively analyse specific challenges and needs of the targeted vulnerable groups.
- Updating their skills to implement suitable and evidence-based strategies to promote the involvement and inclusion of the vulnerable groups.
- Learning how to make the TAISs effective and the ARUs performing in a meaningful, responsible, long-lasting, sustainable, and cooperative way, with constructive monitoring and evaluation of activities.
- Sharing experiences and productively discuss about positive solutions with both peers and experts.
- Improving the use of digital tools for virtual collaboration, participatory approach and inclusive communications.

The Training course was recorded and has been followed by the project's partners and ARU members, live or asynchronously. ARU leaders have also forward the information to external public.

The partners have in fact promoted the plan of the training sessions throughout the ARU members and then also the links to the records available online.

Besides the courses developed by UNIMED, Menedék has also produced a specific course in Hungarian for social workers of other organisations based on the TAIS and sharing the vulnerability concept and jointly showcasing training activities that address that topic.

CESIE also informed that in the case of local stakeholders, only part of them have benefitted from the video session as they were available only in English.

In the case of the Finnish ARU and because of their distinct goals and training for their TAISs, the RAISD Training was not used directly in ARU activities, however several of the training contents were promoted among ARU members and other Finnish stakeholders.

It is not possible instead to have clear data for all the ARUs about how many members have used the training materials, since the course was made publicly available, and it was for this reason also shared with other stakeholders and organisations by some of the ARUs. They were shared with students, migrants, the INTEGRA network which represents a reliable primary source data, gathering multi-stakeholders' perspectives on vulnerability as an intersubjective relation and dependent on actors' viewpoints. Active members of the Network include all quintuple helix stakeholders' representatives and migrant associations and individuals and within the partners institutions.

11 Observatory as a means for future stakeholders' engagement

The Observatory for forced displacement is an initiative of RAISD Project, born with the aim of facilitating access to basic information for forcibly displaced persons, in addition to supporting organisations and research personnel that work day by day to help improve the quality of life of this group. In addition, the Observatory promotes collaboration and awareness raising in host/transit societies and considers the situation of forcibly displaced people within the context of their journey from their countries of origin.

For its own nature, the RAISD Observatory aims to be a virtual space to provide a comprehensive and collaborative forum for interchanging ideas and knowledge among professionals and organisations working in forced migration, putting the needs, challenges and experiences of displaced people at the very core of the initiative. It is designed as an instrument to keep involving stakeholders even after the project lifetime. Among the proposed activities of the Observatory, it wants to enhance the value of civil society organisations' work and make their initiatives, projects, and programs more visible, and at the same time facilitate access to basic information for refugees and asylum seekers. As stated in the Observatory Vision statement, it aims *"To become a lively reference community for the variety of stakeholders working within forced migration that contributes to co-creating initiatives that can improve the life conditions and empower forcibly displaced people."*

Together with the members of the Action Research Units (ARUs), Partners have created the Observatory to serve as a platform for sharing information and experiences, offering opportunities for collaborating in research, assistance and training programs, and providing useful information for forcibly displaced people. It is meant to be a space for stakeholders to engage, share ideas, provide opportunities, and inform interested parties.

Among the activities of the Observatory, some tasks are specifically dedicated to involving stakeholders over time:

- Acknowledging the collaboration of organisations and individuals that have contributed to RAISD and inviting new collaborators to be involved.
- Facilitating networking among organisations or actors to join us.
- Providing a forum and a platform for interchanging ideas among stakeholders.
- Offering work and volunteering opportunities from collaborators.
- Facilitating information and contacts for shared initiatives and projects.

At the time of this document, partners are still brainstorming ideas on roles and responsibilities for the Observatory, to leverage on the potential contributions of all organisations. Among the main inputs emerged by the discussion, it is worth mentioning:

- The Rector of Anadolu University is interested and engaged in the subject of migration and would be positive about the Observatory.
- Partners could establish a network of local hubs in every country, with accredited members and partners as founding members.

- Along with HU team willing to keep contributing, another feasible partner institution for the Observatory would be the Finnish Red Cross, engaged in the project and interested in building a local knowledge base.
- The Observatory can also be a space where to exploit the Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software Tool (CRIOS) developed by RAISD. The CRIOS is a platform that implements several functions, utilities and services to support the collaborative work between different stakeholders, following the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). The CRIOS⁶ could have an important role as a hub for connecting all the participants of the Observatory, with great potential.
- In ten days, 200.000 refugees from Ukraine have arrived in Hungary, causing a change of attitude in the political leaders, much more open towards refugees and willing to cooperate, also meaning that the organisations and persons who work with FDP are seen more positively. Also in Jordan, there is more interest towards the subject due to the Ukrainian war and refugees, and raised the question about what kind of help is most needed in the current situation and how to support them indirectly. This will in turn pose attention on all action related to the refugee-crisis, giving to the Observatory additional relevance.
- The psychology department of Yarmouk University will most likely continue the work started in the TAIS, giving assistance.
- UNIMED offers a large network for disseminating and inviting their associates to take part in the Observatory activities, plus there is a SubNetwork for Migration with about 40 associates, engaged in the issue and that could be invited to collaborate.
- LIU collaboration with UNRWA.
- For UCM it is good and important to think about actions that come natural to the organisations and that create a snowball effect and offer leverages with other activities.

Moreover, during the 4th of November 2021 Consortium meeting, AB members and partners offered some ideas for the project future sustainability and the Observatory, including the following:

- Especially small NGOS (many of the ARU members) are particularly interested in the project and in the TAIS practices, get inspiration and tools from the project. Therefore, it would be good for them to receive future training and resources from the Observatory. Also, the Observatory could collect the dissemination activities of the AB and ARU members, where they mention RAISD and talk about forced migration.
- Students are easy to engage, teachers can use the resources and ideas from the project (available at the Observatory website) for their lessons and projects. Also, FDP can be engaged as volunteers.
- Networking and exchanging information, knowledge, and practices, making research data accessible for new studies and organizing events such as Youth for Change would make the Observatory feasible and interesting for the ARU members.

⁶ More information: <https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/crios/>

The Observatory is an outcome of the RAISD project which expresses the will of the partners to continue the work implemented during the project life span and, more importantly, keep working with the organisations involved in the ARUs. Continuation and sustainability, multiplication, and transferability, are the core elements of the Observatory, and the active participation of the stakeholders is of utmost importance. ARU members are convinced that it is their interest to maintain the ties built during the project's implementation. Sharing project results, new datasets, opinion pieces about new legislation, etc., could be a possible form of engagement, through which collaborating stakeholders can continue to offer their experience.

When asked to point out the organisations which might have an interest in joining the Observatory, partners stated:

- UNHCR's regional office in Budapest, and some NGOs such as Terre des Hommes Foundation, Hungarian Helsinki Committee, Hungarian Baptist Aid and Cordelia Foundation could be interested. We are planning to organise two further ARU meetings before the end of the project, focusing on the Observatory and other possible ways of ensuring the sustainability of the network (Menedék).
- Some organisations have already shown interest and, once defined in more detail, the Observatory will be very well received among ARU members in Spain, even those that were not able to be directly involved in the TAIS implementation. An example of its potential good reception is the statement of a representative of La Merced Migraciones (NGO member of the Spanish ARU): "Information is crucial not to further hinder their inclusion processes and access to rights. Thus, if it is well conceived and that differential step is taken, I think it may be a good idea". Furthermore, not only organisations like NGOs and policy-makers may be interested, but also members of civil society and FDP (UCM).
- The members of the INTEGRA Network could be interested in contributing to the Observatory, that includes already several ARU and AB members as well as local Quintuple Helix Representatives, aiming at: supporting the action of members of political advocacy and whistleblowing groups; sharing opportunities among members for the creation of synergies among initiatives; raising awareness and providing information to employers, job agencies, companies, housing agencies, schools, etc.; providing reciprocal support at general level and for specific cases related to vulnerable people (CESIE).
- The Finnish Red Cross experts on refugee and FDP matters could be interested in using the kind of Observatory that is being designed. They are the key stakeholders who are inclined to work with knowledge-based orientation (HU).
- Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality and Eskişehir Bar Association (AU).
- UNRWA, United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (LIU).
- Interest has been expressed by 1Karmah for Training and Logistic Services and Educational consulting as well as AL-KETAB & AL-SONNA Association (YU).

12 Conclusions

The main conclusions which can be drawn from all the above can be summarised by identifying the positive outcomes of the project and the critical issues, strengths, and threats to be taken into account for the future.

Positive outcomes

All in all, one of the most valuable outputs of the project was the capability of mobilising a wide number of different, heterogeneous actors motivating them to cooperating within the ARUs in order to design and then implement the TAIS. It could not be taken for granted since the very beginning that this venture would be successful and in fact it was not an easy process, due to the many challenges related to the vulnerability contexts under examinations, the recent COVID-19 pandemic as well as a number of criticalities in the implementation of the TAIS. However, the fact that all TAIS have been carried out until the end, in spite of the many unexpected difficulties encountered (the COVID-19 pandemic being the most relevant one at the global level, but not the only one) is a great success of the project, which lays the foundations for its future sustainability. Many individuals and organisations (of different size and scope) have been engaged, not only in the TAIS, but in the many activities that ARUs were able to carry on over time. These bases are strong enough to aim for continuation, transferability, engagement, and future collaborations, propagating the benefits of the project's outcomes beyond the contractual duration.

Another positive outcome is a clear understanding of which are the most relevant stakeholders' categories whose involvement would support the successful achievement of a TAIS. From the analysis carried out in the last phase of the project, it appears that an active involvement of the media is key to guarantee a high visibility of the action and to mobilise positive synergies and a more appropriate dialogue and narrative on migration. A relevant role was (and is) also played by local public administrations, municipalities and local policymakers which, in spite of bureaucratic and administrative obstacles, have shown a high interest and willingness to cooperate in the ARUs.

In one case, the involvement of local actors has even created an awareness about the critical situation of vulnerable groups and changed the attitude of the operators from negative to positive. Moreover, the work in the local context, with the involvement of small associations, NGOs and reception centres, posed the bases for informal networks and continuous synergies, which partners hope to merge into the RAISD Observatory.

Critical issues

In terms of sustainability, one of the key issues is to find ways of keeping the stakeholders' engagement high after the end of the funding phase. This objective is pursued mainly through the implementation of the Observatory as a virtual space for sharing knowledge and networking opportunities, however maintaining it alive after the end of the project calls for a high motivation of a core group of partners committed to carrying it forward. Being sustainability a core element of the RAISD idea and of the TAISs work, the creation and sustainability of the Observatory may be an answer and effective tool to keep the ARU members engaged, but it needs to be addressed carefully by the partners before RAISD ends, to make sure to exploit the project potential. Indeed, this task is being developed in this last phase of RAISD project.

In terms of stakeholder's participation, criticalities have emerged on the capacity of the ARUs to generate a positive and genuine interest from local stakeholders, so as to guarantee their stable participation in the project's activities. A range of different solutions to the challenge have been implemented and tried out, with varying levels of success. Engaging stakeholders in the future stays as an open challenge for the partners, also due to past and possible changes in the members of the ARU itself. Instruments have been designed to make members in the best conditions to work together (the training materials, the minutes of the past meetings, the reports of the piloting experiences), however much will depend on the capacity of the partners to bring valuable stakeholders onboard and on their own willingness to actively contribute to the activities beneficial to VG and FDP. Nevertheless, a good indicator for the potential of the Observatory is the number of organisations and people who have already expressed their interest. Moreover, the ARU leaders are sure that new actors will want to join the initiative.

Final remarks

Whether TAIS will continue to exist, and ARUs will continue to work, is an open question. Still, RAISD and each partner for its own national and local contexts, have been able to mobilise a huge number of individuals and organisations, showing on the one side the great potential of the project idea, and on the other side the high level of interest around the topic. The willingness to work to improve the inclusion measures of the more vulnerable among FDP is with no doubt a priority for many. Whether they will all be able to reach the goal, only time will tell. What we can surely say is that the networking potential of the ARU and the synergy generated by the TAIS will stay. The Observatory will take the legacy of the project and become the key element for the sustainability of RAISD results, collaborations, outcomes and innovative ideas. Partners have already committed resources (both human and technical) to support the dialogue around migration issues, and most likely more resources will come. In this sense, the Observatory will be the hub where the RAISD experiences merge for new joint adventures.

Annex I: statistics of participation in the TAISs

TAIS – Spain (UCM)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	20	23
	Male	3	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Female	14	14
	Male	0	
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	0
	Male	0	
Total			37

TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	6	9
	Male	3	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Female	27	27
	Male	0	
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	102	149
	Male	47	
Total			185

TAIS I – Finland (UH)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	14	21
	Male	5	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Female	0	27

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D6.3 Report on the involvement of local Stakeholders [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , grasia.fdi.ucm.es

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Male	27	
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	4
	Male	4	
Total			52

TAIS II – Finland (UH)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	9	12
	Male	3	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Asylum-seeking families with children		28
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	0
	Male	0	
Total			40

TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	5	8
	Male	2	
Social workers and professionals involved in the analysis	Female	8	10
	Male	2	
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	21	34
	Male	13	
Total			52

TAIS – Turkey (AU)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	6	12
	Male	6	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Female	2	3
	Male	1	
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	37	43
	Male	6	
Total			58

TAIS – Jordan (YU)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	2	8
	Male	6	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Female	42	57
	Male	15	
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	25	40
	Male	15	
Total			105

TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	4	10
	Male	6	
Vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS	Female	18	32
	Male	14	

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
Other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	0
	Male	0	
Total			42

Annex II: statistics of participation in the ARUs

ARU	n. of ARU meetings	Total number of organisations participating in meetings	FDPs
UCM- Spain	11	34	3
CESIE- Italy	20	19	4
UH – Finland	12	7	3
Menedek- Hungary	10	28	4
AU – Turkey	4	21	3
Yarmouk - Jordan	4 workshps, 10 personal meetings, 3 online meetings	8 -- 30 persons	4
LIU - Lebanon	4	4	

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

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D6.3 Report on the involvement of local Stakeholders [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.
t: +34/ 91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es , gracia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.